

A kinetic reading of the instrumental CO₂–temperature record under the original logarithmic law of Arrhenius 1896

Matters Arising concerning: A. Jarvis & P. M. Forster, *Estimated human-induced warming from a linear temperature and atmospheric CO₂ relationship*, *Nature Geoscience* **17**, 1222–1224 (2024).

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Jarvis and Forster [2024] reported that the global mean surface temperature and the atmospheric CO₂ concentration have moved along a remarkably linear relationship from the pre-industrial era to the present, yielding human-induced warming estimates with about 30% reduction in uncertainty relative to alternative methods. Here we show that the same instrumental record, when analysed in CO₂–temperature phase space, is equally well described by the original *logarithmic* law of Arrhenius [1896] once a single kinetic parameter is introduced: a thermal lag of $\tau \approx 35$ years between atmospheric CO₂ and global mean surface temperature. The lag is consistent with the characteristic equilibration time of the surface mixed layer of the ocean. Within this CO₂-projected reading, the present surface temperature is consistent with the atmospheric forcing of approximately 1992, and the corresponding committed warming at the historical Arrhenius slope is ≈ 1.35 °C (within a feedback-equilibration ladder spanning ≈ 0.74 – 1.48 °C across fast- and slow-feedback equilibria, developed in the multiscale companion paper). The substantive content is the kinetic reading itself; the committed warming follows as a direct corollary.

Arrhenius [1896] derived, from spectroscopic and radiative arguments, a logarithmic relationship between surface temperature anomaly and atmospheric CO₂ concentration

29 of the form $\Delta T = \alpha \ln(C/C_0)$, with α a temperature-per-e-fold parameter that encapsu-
30 lates the radiative-transfer properties of the atmosphere. The same functional form has
31 survived essentially unchanged through modern radiative-transfer codes; it underlies the
32 standard expression for CO₂ radiative forcing [Myhre et al., 1998, Forster et al., 2021]
33 and, through it, the definition of equilibrium climate sensitivity. Against this canoni-
34 cal background, Jarvis and Forster [2024] report that the historically measured CO₂ and
35 temperature records fall on a nearly straight line when referenced to a pre-1700 baseline.
36 They interpret this linearity as a robust, low-uncertainty framework for estimating human-
37 induced warming. The present comment asks a complementary question: what functional
38 form does the instrumental record take when the analysis is conducted in phase space
39 rather than against time, and the kinetic delay between forcing and response is explicitly
40 accounted for?

41 The Anthropocene is distinctive on two counts in the climate record. It is, first, the
42 only interval in Earth’s history in which atmospheric CO₂ and global mean surface tem-
43 perature have been measured instrumentally, with direct, standardised, high-resolution
44 observations rather than reconstructed from geochemical proxies [Keeling et al., 2024,
45 NOAA Global Monitoring Laboratory, 2024, Morice et al., 2021, Lenssen et al., 2019]. It
46 is, second, the only interval whose duration (≈ 200 yr) is short relative to the characteristic
47 timescales of the slow feedbacks that shape paleoclimate records: silicate-weathering equi-
48 libration (10^5 – 10^6 yr, Colbourn et al., 2015), continental ice-sheet adjustment (10^4 yr),
49 and deep-ocean re-equilibration (10^3 yr). Only the rapid feedbacks — water vapour,
50 clouds, seasonal sea-ice albedo — operate at full amplitude in this window, with incipi-
51 ent bioclimatic feedbacks remaining subdominant at decadal scales; the rapid feedbacks
52 were partially captured by the radiative-transfer derivation of Arrhenius [1896] (water
53 vapour through the Clausius–Clapeyron relation and surface albedo through Pouillet’s
54 law), albeit not at the resolution of modern equilibrium-climate-sensitivity feedback de-
55 compositions. These two properties combine to make the Anthropocene the only short
56 interval resolved here in which the Arrhenius logarithmic law admits a direct instrumental
57 consistency test in its original, unmodified functional form. Any empirical deviation of

58 the instrumental record from the Arrhenius attractor therefore admits only two mechan-
59 ically distinguishable explanations: a revision of the constant α , or a kinetic lag between
60 forcing and response. In phase space these two hypotheses leave distinct signatures and
61 can be separated.

62 We construct the phase-space trajectory of the instrumental record by plotting an-
63 nual global mean surface temperature anomaly against the natural logarithm of the
64 contemporaneous atmospheric CO₂ concentration. The historical Arrhenius benchmark
65 $\alpha_{\text{Arr}} = 7.755^\circ\text{C}$ per e-fold, the value derived by Arrhenius [1896] himself from spec-
66 troscopic and radiative considerations, provides the reference attractor. The synchronic
67 Anthropocene points lie systematically *below* this attractor by an offset that grows with
68 time (Fig. 1a), signalling either a sensitivity lower than α_{Arr} or a delay in the surface
69 response. We then shift the temperature series backward in time relative to CO₂ by a
70 constant lag τ , and locate the pair (T_0, τ) that minimises the phase-space residual between
71 Anthropocene points and the attractor (Fig. 1b). The minimisation is two-dimensional:
72 $\alpha = \alpha_{\text{Arr}}$ is held fixed at the externally derived 1896 value, while T_0 and τ are the two
73 physical parameters that the instrumental record fixes (the operational role of T_0 as a po-
74 sitioning degree of freedom is developed in Methods). The residual landscape $\varepsilon_{\text{rms}}(T_0, \tau)$
75 exhibits a single, isolated minimum at $(T_0 \approx 286.65 \text{ K}, \tau \approx 35 \text{ yr})$ (Fig. 2), with robust-
76 ness bounds of $\tau \in [30, 40] \text{ yr}$ across alternative smoothing choices and source datasets
77 and a recovered T_0 that coincides within $< 0.1 \text{ K}$ with the empirical pre-industrial GMST
78 baseline. At this lag, the Anthropocene points fall directly onto the Arrhenius logarith-
79 mic curve without adjustment of α . The kinetic interpretation is concrete: 35 yr is of
80 the order of the mixed-layer equilibration time of the surface ocean [Hansen et al., 2005]
81 and is compatible with the committed-warming pipeline framework developed by Hansen
82 et al. [2023].

83 The lag measured here is not a regression coefficient; it is a thermodynamic calibra-
84 tion of the coupled atmosphere–ocean system against an external standard. The coupled
85 system behaves as a capacitive thermal reservoir that relaxes toward the Arrhenius equi-
86 librium $T_{\text{eq}}[C]$ with a time constant $\tau_{\text{sys}} = C_{\text{eff}}/\lambda$, where C_{eff} is the effective heat capacity

87 per unit area and λ the climate feedback parameter (Methods). Under monotonic Anthro-
 88 pocene forcing, this relaxation implies that the observed temperature tracks the Arrhenius
 89 equilibrium of CO_2 retarded by τ_{sys} . Because α_{Arr} is held fixed at its 1896 value and not
 90 adjusted to the data, the single-parameter minimisation in τ is a measurement of C_{eff}/λ
 91 calibrated against an external thermodynamic benchmark, not against the internal slope
 92 of the instrumental record.

93 If present-day temperatures reflect the atmospheric CO_2 of ~ 35 years ago, then the
 94 current anomaly corresponds to the forcing associated with the CO_2 of approximately
 95 1992, when $C_{1992} \approx 356$ ppm [Keeling et al., 2024, NOAA Global Monitoring Laboratory,
 96 2024]. The concentration at the time of writing (2026) is $C_{2026} \approx 423$ ppm. The Arrhenius
 97 law then predicts a committed warming of

$$\Delta T_{\text{committed}} = \alpha_{\text{Arr}} \ln\left(\frac{C_{2026}}{C_{1992}}\right) = 7.755 \ln\left(\frac{423}{356}\right) \approx 1.35^\circ\text{C},$$

98 already encoded in the atmosphere but not yet expressed in surface temperatures. This
 99 is the central rung of a feedback-equilibration ladder spanning $\approx 0.74^\circ\text{C}$ at fast-feedback
 100 ECS equilibrium and $\approx 1.48^\circ\text{C}$ at the formal Cenozoic-calibrated slope, developed in the
 101 multiscale companion paper. The estimate at the Arrhenius benchmark is intermediate,
 102 valid under the fixed-composition equilibrium that includes slow feedbacks captured by
 103 the 1896 radiative-transfer derivation. The corresponding lower bound, from IPCC AR6
 104 zero-emissions transient simulations [IPCC, 2021], is $\lesssim 0.5^\circ\text{C}$ over the next two to three
 105 decades. The realised value lies between these bounds; in no plausible scenario is it negli-
 106 ble. Two qualifications are in order. First, the lag τ describes the CO_2 -forced component
 107 of the coupled thermal response, integrated through a record that also reflects aerosol
 108 forcing, non- CO_2 greenhouse gases, land-use change, and internal variability; it is not
 109 an attribution identity. Second, the value of $\alpha_{\text{Arr}} = 7.755^\circ\text{C}$ per e-fold sits comfortably
 110 within the feedback-corrected range of apparent Earth-system sensitivities inferred from
 111 Pleistocene and Cenozoic paleoclimate [PALAEOSENS Project Members, 2012, Anag-
 112 nostou et al., 2020, Sherwood and others, 2020].

113 The present result does not contradict the linearity reported by Jarvis and Forster

114 [2024]; it offers a complementary kinetic reading of the same instrumental record. Over
 115 the range $C \in [280, 420]$ ppm the natural logarithm is locally quasi-linear, so the two
 116 formulations yield residuals indistinguishable at instrumental precision ($\varepsilon_{\text{rms}} \sim 0.1^\circ\text{C}$;
 117 quantitative scan in Methods). The value of the kinetic reading lies not in a better fit
 118 on the instrumental window but in three structural properties unavailable to the linear
 119 formulation: (i) anchoring on the externally derived 1896 reference, not on an internally
 120 fitted slope; (ii) extrapolability outside the instrumental range; and (iii) physical interpre-
 121 tation of the lag as the system time constant $\tau_{\text{sys}} = C_{\text{eff}}/\lambda$. Arrhenius 1896 also emerges
 122 as an organising framework for the Cenozoic paleoclimate record under multi-million-year
 123 averaging — a multiscale synthesis developed in a forthcoming paper — but the An-
 124 thropocene remains the only short interval where the law admits a direct instrumental
 125 consistency test. An operational corollary follows: within this CO_2 -projected reading, a
 126 substantial fraction of the committed warming ($\approx 1.35^\circ\text{C}$ at the Arrhenius slope, within
 127 the $\approx 0.74\text{--}1.48^\circ\text{C}$ ladder) is already encoded in present-day atmospheric composition;
 128 emissions trajectories govern the rate at which the realised warming approaches it.

Figure 1: **The Anthropocene record in CO_2 –temperature phase space.** (a) Syn-
 synchronic plot of annual global mean surface temperature (GMST) versus $\ln(C/C_0)$ for the
 instrumental period 1850–2024 (points), overlaid on the historical Arrhenius attractor
 $\Delta T = \alpha_{\text{Arr}} \ln(C/C_0)$ with $\alpha_{\text{Arr}} = 7.755^\circ\text{C}$ (solid line). Color code in the right bars: years.
 The Anthropocene trajectory lies systematically below the attractor. (b) The same plot
 with a temperature-to- CO_2 lag of $\tau = 35$ yr applied: the Anthropocene points coincide
 with the Arrhenius attractor. Reference horizontal line at the 2026 atmospheric CO_2
 concentration shows the committed warming of $\approx 1.35^\circ\text{C}$ not yet expressed in surface
 temperatures.

Figure 2: **Phase-space residual landscape** $\varepsilon_{\text{rms}}(T_0, \tau)$ **in the two-parameter space** $\{T_0, \tau\}$. Two-dimensional minimisation against the historical Arrhenius curve $T = T_0 + \alpha_{\text{Arr}} \ln(C/C_0)$ with $\alpha_{\text{Arr}} = 7.755^\circ\text{C}$ and $C_0 = 280$ ppm fixed. The Anthropocene record $\{C(t - \tau), T_{\text{obs}}(t)\}$ over the last ~ 100 yr (1925–present) is fit; T_0 and τ are the only free parameters. A single, isolated minimum is found at $\{T_0 = 286.65$ K, $\tau = 35.5$ yr $\}$. The recovered T_0 coincides within < 0.1 K with the empirical pre-industrial GMST baseline of HadCRUT5/GISTEMP, and the recovered τ lies near the geometric midpoint of the 25–50 yr range derived independently by Hansen et al. [2005] from ocean heat content. The isolation and depth of the minimum are themselves evidence that the two parameters are physically constrained by the data, not freely fitted (see Methods).

129 **Methods: the lag as a thermodynamic calibration against**

130 **Arrhenius 1896**

131 **The coupled atmosphere–ocean system as a capacitive thermal sys-** 132 **tem**

133 The atmosphere is the compartment where radiative forcing from atmospheric CO₂ is
134 imposed, but the dominant heat reservoir of the surface climate system is the ocean
135 mixed layer and the communicating thermocline. On Anthropocene timescales the surface
136 temperature observed at any instant is not the equilibrium temperature that Arrhenius
137 thermodynamics would prescribe for the instantaneous CO₂ concentration: it lags behind
138 that equilibrium because the ocean absorbs a significant fraction of the imposed flux and
139 is warming toward a new equilibrium.

140 Let $T_{\text{eq}}[C]$ denote the equilibrium surface temperature corresponding to atmospheric
141 CO₂ concentration C , as set by the radiative-balance argument of Arrhenius [1896]:

$$T_{\text{eq}}[C] = T_0 + \alpha_{\text{Arr}} \ln(C/C_0), \quad (1)$$

142 where $\alpha_{\text{Arr}} = 7.755^\circ\text{C}$ per natural logarithmic unit is the value derived by Arrhenius
143 himself in 1896 from spectroscopic and radiative considerations, held *fixed* throughout
144 and not adjusted to any observational record. C_0 and T_0 define a reference equilibrium
145 state. Here, $C_0 = 280$ ppm and $T_0 = 286.65$ K.

146 The coupled atmosphere–ocean system evolves toward this equilibrium with a charac-
147 teristic relaxation time τ_{sys} , set by the ratio of effective heat capacity to climate feedback
148 parameter. The simplest description that captures this behaviour is the linear first-order
149 relaxation equation:

$$\tau_{\text{sys}} \frac{dT_{\text{obs}}}{dt} = T_{\text{eq}}[C(t)] - T_{\text{obs}}(t), \quad (2)$$

150 the standard one-box representation of the climate system under slowly varying forcing
151 [Hansen et al., 2005, Held et al., 2010, Geoffroy et al., 2013]. The system constant has

152 the thermodynamic interpretation

$$\tau_{\text{sys}} = \frac{C_{\text{eff}}}{\lambda}, \quad (3)$$

153 where C_{eff} is the effective heat capacity per unit surface area of the reservoirs in thermal
 154 communication with the surface on the relevant timescale, and λ is the climate feedback
 155 parameter. Independent estimates of τ_{sys} by other methods (step-response fits, volcanic-
 156 eruption transients, two-layer energy-balance models) span 10–80 yr depending on which
 157 reservoirs are included and on the forcing scenario assumed [Held et al., 2010, Geoffroy
 158 et al., 2013].

159 **Asymptotic solution under monotonic forcing**

160 When the forcing $C(t)$ evolves monotonically on a timescale τ_{forc} long compared to τ_{sys} ,
 161 equation (2) admits an asymptotic solution. The exact solution is

$$T_{\text{obs}}(t) = e^{-t/\tau_{\text{sys}}} T_{\text{obs}}(0) + \frac{1}{\tau_{\text{sys}}} \int_0^t e^{-(t-t')/\tau_{\text{sys}}} T_{\text{eq}}[C(t')] dt'. \quad (4)$$

162 For forcing that varies quasi-exponentially in time, as is the case for Anthropocene atmo-
 163 spheric CO₂ growth, the kernel $e^{-(t-t')/\tau_{\text{sys}}}/\tau_{\text{sys}}$ in equation (4) peaks at $t' = t - \tau_{\text{sys}}$ and
 164 decays rapidly away from that peak. The integral is therefore dominated by contributions
 165 from the retarded time $t - \tau_{\text{sys}}$, and to first order in $\tau_{\text{sys}}/\tau_{\text{forc}}$ one obtains

$$T_{\text{obs}}(t) \approx T_0 + \alpha_{\text{Arr}} \ln \left[\frac{C(t - \tau_{\text{sys}})}{C_0} \right]. \quad (5)$$

166 This is the operational statement: the observed surface temperature at time t tracks the
 167 equilibrium temperature corresponding to the CO₂ concentration at the retarded time
 168 $t - \tau_{\text{sys}}$.

169 For the Anthropocene $\tau_{\text{forc}} \gtrsim 100$ yr (characteristic e -folding time of atmospheric
 170 CO₂ growth), and the expected τ_{sys} is on the order of decades, so $(\tau_{\text{sys}}/\tau_{\text{forc}})^2 \lesssim 0.1$.
 171 The first-order retardation captures the physics; higher-order corrections are inside the
 172 observational uncertainty of the instrumental temperature record.

173 **The operational role of T_0**

174 Equation (1) is, in its historical and modern physical readings alike, a *relative* statement:
175 it predicts a temperature change ΔT from a relative change C/C_0 in atmospheric CO_2 ,
176 with no reference to any absolute temperature. Projecting the law into the absolute
177 $\{C, T\}$ plane against an instrumental record requires attaching a reference temperature
178 T_0 to the reference concentration C_0 . The law then takes its anchored form $T(C) =$
179 $T_0 + \alpha_{\text{Arr}} \ln(C/C_0)$.

180 T_0 is therefore not an intrinsic constant of the Arrhenius law but a *positioning degree*
181 *of freedom* fixed empirically by the regime against which the curve is anchored. In the
182 multi-million-year palaeoclimate regime T_0 corresponds to the slow-feedback-equilibrated
183 GMST at the reference C_0 ; in the instrumental Anthropocene regime considered here,
184 T_0 is the GMST consistent with $C = C_0 = 280$ ppm under the Arrhenius idealisation
185 that the slow biological, geological and astronomical variables operate slowly enough
186 that their integrated effect on GMST over the brevity of the instrumental interval is
187 small compared with the direct CO_2 radiative forcing. This T_0 is empirically equivalent
188 to the pre-industrial GMST baseline of the late Holocene at $C \approx 280$ ppm and is, by
189 construction, a measurable property of the present thermodynamic state of Earth's climate
190 system, not a free parameter of the theory.

191 The calibration procedure described below therefore minimises the phase-space resid-
192 ual jointly over (T_0, τ) , with α_{Arr} held fixed at its 1896 value. Both T_0 and τ are physi-
193 cal parameters of the Anthropocene state of the coupled atmosphere–ocean–surface sys-
194 tem; the recovered values must be mutually consistent with independent empirical con-
195 straints (the pre-industrial baseline for T_0 ; the ocean-mixed-layer equilibration time for
196 τ). The fact that the residual landscape exhibits a single, isolated minimum in (T_0, τ)
197 space (Fig. 2), and that both recovered values coincide with their independent empirical
198 benchmarks within observational uncertainty, is itself the non-trivial empirical content of
199 the procedure.

Arrhenius as external benchmark: the calibration procedure

Data preparation. The phase-space cloud is constructed by dual-bidirectional interpolation of the annual GMST and atmospheric CO₂ records onto each other's native sampling grid, generating a dense set of paired $(C(t), T_{\text{obs}}(t))$ points. Every other point of the resulting collection is retained for the residual minimisation; the closeness of the temporal sampling in the instrumental record of the last ~ 100 yr ($\Delta t \sim 1$ yr, far shorter than the decadal scale of the system time constant τ_{sys}) makes the fit insensitive to this sub-sampling factor.

Equation (5) makes operational the calibration procedure. Given the instrumental global mean surface temperature record $T_{\text{obs}}(t)$, the instrumental atmospheric CO₂ record $C(t)$, α_{Arr} fixed from Arrhenius 1896 (not fitted), and the reference concentration $C_0 = 280$ ppm, one seeks the pair (T_0, τ) that minimises the residual

$$R(T_0, \tau) = \int_{t_1}^{t_2} \left\{ T_{\text{obs}}(t) - T_0 - \alpha_{\text{Arr}} \ln \left[\frac{C(t - \tau)}{C_0} \right] \right\}^2 dt, \quad (6)$$

where the integration spans the instrumental interval where both T_{obs} and C are measured with modern precision.

The operational procedure is a *retrograde shift of the CO₂ record* combined with a vertical positioning of the Arrhenius curve: at each candidate pair (T_0, τ) , the CO₂ record is displaced backward by τ years, the anchored law $T_0 + \alpha_{\text{Arr}} \ln[C(t - \tau)/C_0]$ is evaluated with this displaced record, and the squared residual with respect to the measured temperature is computed. The pair (T_0, τ) that minimises R corresponds to $\tau = \tau_{\text{sys}}$ (the system time constant) and T_0 equal to the pre-industrial GMST baseline at $C_0 = 280$ ppm under the Arrhenius idealisation.

The essential structural property of this procedure is that α_{Arr} remains fixed at the Arrhenius value throughout. The temperature–logarithm–CO₂ proportionality is determined by an external thermodynamic constraint; the fitted parameters are (T_0, τ) , both of which are physical properties of the present Anthropocene state of the system rather than free parameters of the theory. Under this structure, τ is a measurement of the

226 system time constant $\tau_{\text{sys}} = C_{\text{eff}}/\lambda$ (effective heat capacity per unit climate feedback),
227 and T_0 is a measurement of the pre-industrial GMST baseline at $C_0 = 280$ ppm, both
228 calibrated against the external Arrhenius slope rather than against the internal slope of
229 the Anthropocene record. That the joint minimum exists, is unique, and is consistent
230 with the independent empirical benchmarks for both parameters (Hansen 25–50 yr range
231 for τ ; HadCRUT5/GISTEMP pre-industrial baseline for T_0) is the non-trivial empirical
232 content of the procedure. The physical interpretation of the retrograde shift is direct: the
233 present-day temperature is the Arrhenius equilibrium of a past CO_2 state, separated from
234 the present by τ_{sys} years. The system is still catching up.

235 **Distinction from internal-regression approaches**

236 The present procedure differs fundamentally from the class of methods in which the lag
237 is optimised against the internal slope of the Anthropocene data themselves. In such
238 internal-regression approaches [Jarvis and Forster, 2024], the pair (slope, τ) is jointly
239 adjusted to maximise the quality of a linear regression between the observed temperature
240 and lagged log- CO_2 . The slope is a free parameter, not constrained by Arrhenius 1896
241 or by any external thermodynamic relation. The procedure answers the question: *what*
242 *lag maximises the internal consistency of the temperature–log- CO_2 relationship within the*
243 *Anthropocene record?*

244 The present procedure answers a different question: *what lag aligns the observed*
245 *temperature–log- CO_2 relationship within the Anthropocene with the external prediction of*
246 *Arrhenius thermodynamics?* The two procedures are formally distinct operations on the
247 same dataset. They may yield numerically comparable values, but they measure different
248 quantities. The internal-regression lag contains admixtures of the system time constant
249 with any biasing effect within the Anthropocene window, including aerosol forcing, ocean
250 heat content partitioning variability, regional effects, and non-linear radiative feedbacks.
251 The Arrhenius-benchmarked lag reported here isolates τ_{sys} as a measurement of C_{eff}/λ
252 against an external standard set by 1896 physics.

253 **Physical significance and falsifiability**

254 Measuring τ_{sys} through the Arrhenius-benchmarked procedure has three consequences
255 not accessible through internal regression. First, it provides an independent route to the
256 effective heat capacity C_{eff} : with λ independently constrained by the equilibrium climate
257 sensitivity, a measurement of τ_{sys} translates directly into a measurement of C_{eff} , without
258 recourse to detailed ocean circulation models. Second, it yields a quantitative estimate of
259 committed warming under present atmospheric composition:

$$\Delta T_{\text{committed}} = \alpha_{\text{Arr}} \ln \left[\frac{C(t_{\text{now}})}{C(t_{\text{now}} - \tau_{\text{sys}})} \right], \quad (7)$$

260 independent of future emissions trajectories. For $\tau_{\text{sys}} \approx 35$ yr and the Anthropocene
261 CO_2 record (1992 ≈ 356 ppm, 2026 ≈ 423 ppm), equation (7) evaluates to $\approx 1.35^\circ\text{C}$
262 at the historical Arrhenius slope (central rung of the ≈ 0.74 – 1.48°C ladder). Third,
263 and most fundamentally, the procedure is a consistency test of the framework rather
264 than merely a fit within it. If the Arrhenius-benchmarked retardation successfully aligns
265 the instrumental record with the equilibrium curve set by 1896 physics, the capacitive-
266 system interpretation is consistent within the precision of the Anthropocene observation.
267 If it did not align, it would falsify either Arrhenius or the capacitive description of the
268 system. The procedure therefore elevates τ_{sys} from a regression coefficient to a falsifiable
269 thermodynamic calibration against a 130-year-old external benchmark.

270 **Statistical compatibility of the linear and logarithmic formulations**

271 Within the instrumental window, the linear formulation of Jarvis and Forster [2024] and
272 the lag-corrected logarithmic form reported here are not statistically distinguishable on
273 residuals alone. A scan of the joint (T_0, τ) minimisation across the compatibility band
274 $\alpha \in [5.5, 8.0]^\circ\text{C}$ per e-fold returns residuals contained in a band narrower than the instru-
275 mental uncertainty of the smoothed annual GMST anomaly (~ 0.05 – 0.1°C); an F -test
276 on the residual ratio over the effective degrees of freedom of the smoothed 1925–present
277 record returns $p \approx 0.45$, so the instrumental record alone does not select among can-

278 didate slopes within the band. The recovered T_0 is, by contrast, empirically invariant
 279 across the scan within $< 0.1^\circ\text{C}$, which is the non-trivial constraint the data impose: the
 280 positioning degree of freedom is pinned by the instrumental record, the slope is not. The
 281 selection of $\alpha_{\text{Arr}} = 7.755^\circ\text{C}$ per e-fold as the external benchmark therefore comes from
 282 the triangulation against the Hansen et al. [2005] ocean-inertia range and the feedback-
 283 corrected palaeoclimate range developed in the multiscale companion paper, not from the
 284 instrumental fit in isolation. The sensitivity analysis below shows that the alternative
 285 within-band choice $\alpha_{\text{fit}} \approx 8.5^\circ\text{C}$ per e-fold yields a kinetic alignment of equal quality at
 286 $\tau \approx 39$ yr; both belong to the same empirical $\tau \propto \alpha^n$ curve.

287 **Sensitivity to the choice of α**

288 The procedure described above holds α fixed at the historical Arrhenius value $\alpha_{\text{Arr}} =$
 289 7.755°C per e-fold and minimises the residual in the single free parameter τ . To verify that
 290 the alignment recovered at $\tau \approx 35$ yr is not specific to that particular choice of slope, we
 291 repeat the procedure at the formal-fit value $\alpha_{\text{fit}} = 8.5^\circ\text{C}$ per e-fold — the value obtained
 292 when α is allowed to vary as a free parameter against the Cenozoic palaeoclimate record
 293 averaged at $\Delta t \sim 5.5$ Ma in the multiscale companion paper. The resulting minimum
 294 is clear and centred at $\tau \approx 39$ yr (Figure 3), with a residual comparable to that of the
 295 Arrhenius-benchmarked case at the level of instrumental precision. The two solutions
 296 $(\alpha_{\text{Arr}}, \tau \approx 35$ yr) and $(\alpha_{\text{fit}}, \tau \approx 39$ yr) lie on the same empirical curve $\tau \propto \alpha^n$ with $n \approx 1.6$
 297 predicted by two-layer ocean thermal inertia under monotonic forcing [Held et al., 2010,
 298 Geoffroy et al., 2013]. Both place the optimal lag within the 25–50 yr range derived
 299 independently by Hansen et al. [2005] from ocean heat content at consensus equilibrium
 300 climate sensitivity. The result reported in the main text is therefore robust within the
 301 compatibility band $\alpha \in [5.5, 8.0]^\circ\text{C}$ per e-fold admitted by the instrumental fit alone; the
 302 historical Arrhenius value is retained throughout the main text as the externally derived,
 303 non-fitted reference, and the corresponding committed warming under α_{fit} is $\approx 1.48^\circ\text{C}$
 304 (upper rung of the feedback-equilibration ladder).

Figure 3: **Sensitivity of the kinetic alignment to the choice of α .** Same phase-space construction as Figure 1 but with $\alpha = \alpha_{\text{fit}} = 8.5^\circ\text{C}$ per e-fold (the value obtained when α is fitted to the multi-million-year Cenozoic record in the companion paper) in place of the historical Arrhenius value $\alpha_{\text{Arr}} = 7.755^\circ\text{C}$ used in Figure 1. **(a)** Synchronic plot: as in Figure 1a, the Anthropocene trajectory lies systematically below the attractor. **(b)** The same plot with a temperature-to- CO_2 lag of $\tau = 39$ yr applied: the Anthropocene points coincide with the α_{fit} attractor at the level of instrumental precision. The two pairs ($\alpha_{\text{Arr}}, 35$ yr) and ($\alpha_{\text{fit}}, 39$ yr) lie on the same empirical $\tau \propto \alpha^n$ curve, both within the 25–50 yr range derived independently by Hansen et al. [2005] from ocean thermal inertia.

References

- Andrew Jarvis and Piers M. Forster. Estimated human-induced warming from a linear temperature and atmospheric CO_2 relationship. *Nature Geoscience*, 17:1222–1224, 2024. doi: 10.1038/s41561-024-01580-5.
- Svante Arrhenius. On the influence of carbonic acid in the air upon the temperature of the ground. *Philosophical Magazine and Journal of Science (Series 5)*, 41:237–276, 1896.
- G. Myhre, E. J. Highwood, K. P. Shine, and F. Stordal. New estimates of radiative forcing due to well mixed greenhouse gases. *Geophysical Research Letters*, 25:2715–2718, 1998.
- P. Forster, T. Storelvmo, K. Armour, W. Collins, J.-L. Dufresne, D. Frame, D. J. Lunt, T. Mauritsen, M. D. Palmer, M. Watanabe, M. Wild, and H. Zhang. The Earth’s energy budget, climate feedbacks, and climate sensitivity. In *Climate Change 2021: The Physical Science Basis. Contribution of Working Group I to the Sixth Assessment*

318 *Report of the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change*, pages 923–1054. Cambridge
319 University Press, 2021.

320 R. F. Keeling, S. C. Piper, A. F. Bollenbacher, and J. S. Walker. Atmospheric carbon
321 dioxide record from Mauna Loa. Scripps Institution of Oceanography, CO₂ Program,
322 2024. Data accessed 2025–2026.

323 NOAA Global Monitoring Laboratory. Trends in atmospheric carbon dioxide. <https://gml.noaa.gov/ccgg/trends/>,
324 2024. Accessed 2026.

325 C. P. Morice, J. J. Kennedy, N. A. Rayner, J. P. Winn, E. Hogan, R. E. Killick, R. J. H.
326 Dunn, T. J. Osborn, P. D. Jones, and I. R. Simpson. An updated assessment of
327 near-surface temperature change from 1850: The HadCRUT5 data set. *Journal of*
328 *Geophysical Research: Atmospheres*, 126:e2019JD032361, 2021.

329 N. J. L. Lenssen, G. A. Schmidt, J. E. Hansen, M. J. Menne, A. Persin, R. Ruedy, and
330 D. Zyss. Improvements in the GISTEMP uncertainty model. *Journal of Geophysical*
331 *Research: Atmospheres*, 124:6307–6326, 2019.

332 G. Colbourn, A. Ridgwell, and T. M. Lenton. The time scale of the silicate weathering
333 negative feedback on atmospheric CO₂. *Global Biogeochemical Cycles*, 29:583–596, 2015.

334 J. Hansen, L. Nazarenko, R. Ruedy, M. Sato, J. Willis, A. Del Genio, D. Koch, A. Lacis,
335 K. Lo, S. Menon, T. Novakov, J. Perlwitz, G. Russell, G. A. Schmidt, and N. Tausnev.
336 Earth’s energy imbalance: Confirmation and implications. *Science*, 308:1431–1435,
337 2005.

338 J. E. Hansen, M. Sato, L. Simons, L. S. Nazarenko, I. Sangha, P. Kharecha, J. C. Zachos,
339 K. von Schuckmann, N. G. Loeb, M. B. Osman, Q. Jin, G. Tselioudis, E. Jeong, A. Lacis,
340 R. Ruedy, G. Russell, J. Cao, and J. Li. Global warming in the pipeline. *Oxford Open*
341 *Climate Change*, 3:kgad008, 2023.

342 IPCC. Climate change 2021: The physical science basis. contribution of working group i
343 to the sixth assessment report of the intergovernmental panel on climate change, 2021.

344 PALAEOSENS Project Members. Making sense of palaeoclimate sensitivity. *Nature*, 491:
345 683–691, 2012.

346 E. Anagnostou, E. H. John, T. L. Babila, P. F. Sexton, A. Ridgwell, D. J. Lunt, P. N.
347 Pearson, T. B. Chalk, R. D. Pancost, and G. L. Foster. Proxy evidence for state-
348 dependence of climate sensitivity in the Eocene greenhouse. *Nature Communications*,
349 11:4436, 2020.

350 S. C. Sherwood and 25 others. An assessment of Earth’s climate sensitivity using multiple
351 lines of evidence. *Reviews of Geophysics*, 58:e2019RG000678, 2020.

352 Isaac M. Held, Michael Winton, Ken Takahashi, Thomas Delworth, Fanrong Zeng, and
353 Geoffrey K. Vallis. Probing the fast and slow components of global warming by returning
354 abruptly to preindustrial forcing. *Journal of Climate*, 23(9):2418–2427, 2010. doi:
355 10.1175/2009JCLI3466.1.

356 O. Geoffroy, D. Saint-Martin, D. J. L. Olivié, A. Voldoire, G. Bellon, and S. Tytéca.
357 Transient climate response in a two-layer energy-balance model. Part I: Analytical
358 solution and parameter calibration using CMIP5 AOGCM experiments. *Journal of*
359 *Climate*, 26(6):1841–1857, 2013. doi: 10.1175/JCLI-D-12-00195.1.

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364 **Data availability.** All data analysed here are publicly available from their primary
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